

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some Enamino Ketones and Esters of Bis(2-pyrazolyl)ketones and sulphones

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Manuscript received 12 May 1993, accepted 28 June 1993

The enamino ketones and esters (2-5) have been obtained by the condensation of bis(4-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)-ketones and sulphones (1) with acetylacetone, dimedone and methyl/ethyl acetoacetate. Their spectra have been correlated to their structures. The antimicrobial activity of the compounds have also been assayed.

The chemistry of enamines has assumed importance mainly due to their versatile utility as synthons in the synthesis of many organic compounds¹. The carbonyl and sulphonyl activated multiple bonds serve as important pharmacophores². The pyrazolines derived from these moieties are indeed biologically potent³. It was therefore felt that the enamines of the pyrazolines which contain another pharmacophore might increase the potency considerably. Further, earlier reports reveal that conjugated enamino ketones and esters derived from simple dialkylamines, cyclic amines and

heteroaro-matic compounds are known. However, there is no report about the enamines of bis(2-pyrazolyl)-ketones and sulphones.

Results and Discussion

In order to synthesise such novel compounds (2-5), bis(2-pyrazolyl)ketones and sulphones (1) have been condensed with acetylacetone, dimedone and methyl/ethyl acetoacetate in refluxing benzene for 6-8 h (Scheme 1, Table 1). The products (2-5) have been obtained in fairly good yields by simple method.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–5*

Comp no	X	R %	Yield °C	M p
2 a	CO	H	72	216–18
b	CO	4-OCH ₃	67	256–58
c	CO	4-Cl	78	236–37
d	SO ₂	H	64	219–20
e	SO ₂	4-OCH ₃	60	261–63
f	SO ₂	4-Cl	71	297–99
3 a	CO	H	74	195–96
b	CO	4-OCH ₃	68	238–39
c	CO	4-Cl	77	231–32
d	SO ₂	H	67	225–26
e	SO ₂	4-OCH ₃	58	273–75
f	SO ₂	4-Cl	69	>300
4 a	CO	H	75	162–63
b	CO	4-OCH ₃	61	194–95
c	CO	4-Cl	80	183–84
d	SO ₂	H	68	186–87
e	SO ₂	4-OCH ₃	56	216–17
f	SO ₂	4-Cl	77	238–40
5 a	CO	H	78	145–46
b	CO	4-OCH ₃	68	178–79
c	CO	4-Cl	74	160–61
d	SO ₂	H	66	178–79
e	SO ₂	4-OCH ₃	61	201–02
f	SO ₂	4-Cl	68	215–17

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses.

Ir spectra of 2–5 did not exhibit a band around 3360–3260 cm⁻¹ characteristic of N–H stretching frequency⁴ indicating that this is involved

in the condensation reaction forming a C=C bond. The presence of bands at 1615–1570 (C=O)⁵, 1740–1665, 1640–1635 (C=O)⁶, 1565–1535 (C=N)⁶ and 1340–1330, 1150–1135 cm⁻¹ (SO₂)^{7,8} are in accordance with the structured assignments.

A signal observed at δ 5.00–5.25 for olefinic proton in the ¹H nmr spectra of 2–5 supports the formation of enamines⁹. This is substantiated by the absence of a broad singlet usually observed at δ 5.50–6.60 for N–H of pyrazoline moiety^{7,8}. The methine and methylene protons of the pyrazoline ring displayed an AMX pattern as is observed in the parent molecules¹⁰. Each proton appeared as a doublet of doublet at δ 4.53–4.96 (H_A), 4.19–4.39 (H_M) and 3.49–4.13 (H_X) (Table 2). The δ _H values observed at δ 1.26–1.28, 2.12–2.82 (CH₃), 2.26–2.84 (CH₂), 3.75–3.76 (OCH₃), 4.12–4.16 (OCH₂CH₃) and 1.17–1.18, 1.20–1.22 [*gem*-(CH₃)₂] are due to the other functionalities of the enamine part. The aromatic protons of 2–5 appear as multiplets at δ 6.76–7.66.

The ¹³C nmr (δ , ppm) spectra exhibited δ _c values for α - and β -carbons of enamino ketones (2, 3) around 102 and 157 while for enamino esters (4, 5) at 92 and 155¹¹. The δ _c values

TABLE 2—PMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ ppm) OF 2–5

Compd no	δ -CH	H _A	H _M	H _X	Coupling constant (Hz)		
					J _{AM}	J _{AX}	J _{MX}
2 a	5.46	4.86	4.32	3.80	11.5	5.6	10.8
c	5.21	4.74	4.19	3.78	11.5	5.6	10.8
d	5.23	4.84	4.33	3.90	12.5	5.6	10.6
f	5.23	4.88	4.35	3.95	12.5	5.6	10.6
3 a	5.25	4.56	4.24	3.52	11.5	5.5	10.7
b	5.26	4.53	4.21	3.49	11.5	5.5	10.8
d	5.27	4.87	4.44	3.98	12.5	5.5	10.6
e	5.25	4.88	4.42	3.94	12.5	5.5	10.6
4 a	5.02	4.68	4.25	3.92	11.5	5.5	10.7
b	5.00	4.66	4.23	3.91	11.5	5.6	10.8
d	5.12	4.94	4.29	4.13	12.5	5.6	10.6
e	5.10	4.89	4.26	4.11	12.5	5.6	10.6
5 a	5.24	4.70	4.35	4.05	11.5	5.5	10.7
c	5.18	4.75	4.36	4.08	11.5	5.5	10.7
d	5.23	4.92	4.39	4.12	12.6	5.6	10.6
f	5.21	4.96	4.34	4.10	12.6	5.6	10.6

TABLE 3—¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ ppm) OF 2–5

Compd no.	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6	C-2'	C-3'
2a	154.48	48.96	57.88	183.72	156.02	102.34
f	156.06	50.01	58.47	–	156.18	102.82
3a	155.35	49.78	57.66	183.74	102.46	157.76
d	156.48	49.98	57.89	–	102.40	157.71
4b	154.86	49.73	57.68	182.87	155.32	92.39
e	156.54	49.12	57.82	–	155.48	92.64
5a	155.46	48.94	57.84	182.94	155.34	92.46
f	157.96	49.62	58.02	–	155.39	92.54

for pyrazoline ring carbons appeared almost in the same region as in the parent molecules at 154.48–159.96 (C-3), 48.94–50.01 (C-4) and 57.66–58.47 (C-5) [15,16] (Table 3). The resonance signal due to carbonyl carbon (C-6) of the bis(2-pyrazolyl)ketone has been observed at 182–183. However, ¹³C chemical shift values at 196–198 and 168–169 are assigned to carbonyl carbon of ketone (C-4' or C-1') and ester (C-4') moieties of the enamine part. The δ_c values observed at 15.21–15.28 (C-1'), 50.32–50.36 (C-4'), 15.68, 32.66–32.69, 50.63–59.64 (C-5'), 14.06–14.08, 39.48–39.52 (C-6'), 28.41–28.42 (C-7'), 28.82–28.84 (C-8') are attributed to different carbons of other functional groups present in the enamine unit of 2–5.

The mass spectra of 2d, 3a, 4a and 5d have been recorded at 70 eV as representatives of each system in order to establish their structures. Appearance of peaks corresponding to 4-phenyl-*N*-substituted-2-pyrazolyl cation (100%) and *M* + 1 ion are common features in all these systems. The α-cleavage and pyrazoline ring cleavage processes are predominant in the fission of these molecular ions^{7,12}. It is rather surprising to observe that neither CO nor SO₂ has been lost from their molecular ions thereby confirming their stabilities. The ketone or ester moiety of an enamine part remains intact during the disintegration in certain instances¹³. However, during the scission of the molecular ion of 3d, dimedone moiety remains unaffected. The dominant daughter ions derived from their molecular ions and further cleavage processes involved in them suggest the

existence of possible key intermediates thereby confirming the structures.

Biological activity : All the compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against the organisms *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis* (gram + ve) and *E. coli* (gram –ve) by filter paper disc method¹⁴ and found to be active. Amongst them the enamino derivatives of bis(2-pyrazolyl)sulphones showed greater activity than the corresponding bis(2-pyrazolyl)ketones. The compounds 2–5 were also assayed for antifungal activity against the organisms *E. coli*, *F. solani*, *C. lunata* and *H. oryzae* by Horsfall and Rich method¹⁵. All the tested compounds effectively inhibited spore germination of the three fungi at 1 mg ml⁻¹. The results of the investigation reveal that all the compounds possess relatively high inhibitory effect over *F. solani* and *C. lunata* compared to *H. oryzae*. It is observed that the halogen or methoxy substituents in the phenyl moiety enhances the antifungal activity compared to other substituents. Moreover, all the compounds containing sulphone moiety displayed greater antimicrobial activity in comparison to those containing carbonyl group. Apart from these, the enaminoesters of bis(2-pyrazolyl)ketones and sulphones (4,5) exhibited greater activity than their enamino ketones (2,3).

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃)

on a Bruker spectrometer (400 and 50.28 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Finnigan Mat 1020 B spectrometer at an ionising voltage of 70 eV. The elemental analyses were performed at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Punjab University, Chandigarh.

*Enamino ketones and esters of bis(2-pyrazolyl)ketones and sulphones (2-5). General procedure*¹⁶: A mixture of bis(4-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)- ketone or sulphone (**1**; 0.01 mol) and an appropriate ketone or ester (0.02 mol) in benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 5-7 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored at intervals by tlc. After completion of the reaction, most of the solvent was removed by distillation and the residual portion was treated with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°). The contents were then refrigerated overnight. The product formed was collected by filtration, washed, dried and then recrystallised from ethyl acetate. The purity of the product was ascertained by tlc.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.P.) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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